

Synthesis, structural and thermal characterization and antifungal study of manganese(II), iron(III), cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes of N,O donor ligands

V. G. Mane^a, V. N. Patange^b and B. R. Arbad^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jawahar Arts, Science and Commerce College, Andure, Tuljapur, Osmanabad-413 603, Maharashtra, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : abr_chem@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The solid complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff bases derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-(2H)-pyran-2,4(3H)dione (dehydroacetic acid) and 3-chloroaniline and 3-aminophenol, have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, conductometry, thermal analysis, magnetic, IR, NMR, UV-Vis spectral studies and X-ray powder diffraction. From the analytical data the stoichiometry of the complexes has been found to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand). The low conductance values suggest that the complexes are non-electrolytes. IR spectral data suggest that the ligand behaves as a dibasic bidentate ligand with N : O donor sequence towards metal ions. The kinetic parameters (*n*, *E*, *Z*, ΔS and *G*) estimated using Coats-Redfern (C.R.), MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.) and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.) methods are in good mutual agreement. The powder X-ray diffraction study suggests that the complex has monoclinic crystal system with P2/m space group. The physico-chemical data suggests that all the complexes possess octahedral geometry. They are also screened for antifungal activity.

Keywords : Dehydroacetic acid, transition metal complexes, Schiff bases, thermal analysis.

Dehydroacetic acid is an important biologically active compound, it has antibiotic, fungicidal¹, antiseptic² effects and used to enhance vitamin-C stability and protect vegetables during food processing³. It is well known from the literature that dehydroacetic acid moiety have a strong ability to form metal complexes. The number of Schiff bases of dehydroacetic acid with primary aliphatic, aryl amines are reported in literature. Schiff bases play a prominent role in biological applications due to excellent chelating capacity in modern coordination chemistry⁴. The extensive work in coordination complexes have been made possible with the help of various experimental techniques and has led to a number of interesting conclusions⁵. In view of the fact that *meta* substituted aromatic amines have not yet been investigated by workers, we report here the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions with ligands (Fig. 1), 3-[3-chloro-phenylimino-ethyl]-6-methyl-pyrane-2,4-dion (L₁) and 3-[3-hydroxy-phenylimino-ethyl]-6-methyl-pyrane-2,4-dion (L₂), derived from condensation of DHA and 3-chloro aniline and 3-amino phenol respectively.

For L₁, R = Cl and for L₂, R = OH

Fig. 1. Structure of ligand

Results and discussion

All the complexes are coloured solids, stable to air and non-hygroscopic in nature. They decompose at high temperature without melting. They are insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in common non-polar organic solvents. The molar conductance values 4.56 to 16.20 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for $10^{-4} M$ solution of metal complexes in DMF indicates that the metal complexes are non-electrolytic in nature¹⁰. The elemental analysis reveal mononuclear nature and 1 : 2 composition of M : L. The analytical results of complexes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands and its complexes

Compd./ Complex	Color	Elemental analysis (%) :					Mol. wt.	M.p./ Decompo- sition (°C)	λ_m (mho cm ² mol ⁻¹)
		Found (Calcd.)							
		C	H	N	Cl	M			
C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClNO ₃ (L ₁)	White	59.80 (60.55)	3.68 (4.36)	4.85 (5.04)	12.26 (12.77)	-	277.71	120	
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cu]	Violet	48.23 (48.75)	3.49 (3.51)	4.05 (4.06)	19.86 (20.56)	8.94 (9.21)	689.86	> 270	4.56
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Co]	Pink	50.77 (49.08)	3.12 (3.53)	3.94 (4.09)	19.34 (20.70)	7.86 (8.60)	685.25	> 270	9.3
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Mn]	Dark brown	48.82 (49.37)	3.47 (3.53)	4.02 (4.11)	20.14 (20.82)	8.02 (8.06)	681.25	> 270	16.2
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Fe]Cl	Brown	46.46 (46.80)	3.455 (3.51)	4.001 (3.90)	24.17 (24.67)	7.07 (7.77)	718.62	> 270	3.8
C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₄ (L ₂)	White	64.01 (64.86)	4.85 (5.05)	4.85 (5.4)	-	-	259.26	168	
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Cu]	Dark brown	51.10 (51.50)	3.49 (4.01)	4.05 (4.29)	9.64 (10.86)	9.44 (9.73)	652.97	> 270	8.5
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Co]	Light green	50.77 (51.87)	3.96 (4.04)	3.94 (4.32)	10.01 (10.94)	8.86 (9.09)	648.35	267	9.3
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Mn]	Dark brown	51.02 (52.19)	3.79 (4.07)	4.29 (4.35)	10.48 (11.00)	8.42 (8.53)	644.36	220	15.3
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Fe]Cl	Brown	48.46 (49.33)	3.55 (3.99)	4.00 (4.11)	15.00 (15.60)	8.07 (8.19)	681.73	> 270	11.2

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands have been recorded in CDCl₃. The spectra of L₁ shows sharp peaks at 1.75 (1H, s, pyran C₃-H), 2.17 (3H, s, pyran C₆-CH₃), 5.77 (1H, s, pyrane C₅-H), 15.94 (1H, s, enolic OH for DHA moiety) and 2.60 (3H, s, CH₃-C=N). The phenyl moiety values 7.1–7.55 (4H, m, for Ar-H).

The ¹H NMR spectra of L₂ shows sharp peaks at 1.60 (1H, s, pyran C₃-H), 2.45 (3H, s, pyran C₆-CH₃), 5.80 (1H, s, pyrane C₅-H), 15.4.7 (1H, s, enolic OH for DHA moiety), 2.58 (3H, s, CH₃-C=N) and 4.38 (1H, s, phenolic OH). The phenyl moiety values 7.00–7.40 (4H, m, for Ar-H).

IR spectra : The IR spectra of ligands shows bands at 3362–3364, 1702–1715, 1650–1660, 1436–1440 and 1629–1634 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) are assigned to νOH (hydrogen bonded), νC=O (lactone), νC=N (azomethine), νC–N (aryl azomethine) and νC=O (enolic) vibrations respectively. The ligands in the present work are in tautomeric form. The carbonyl group may be in keto form or in enol form¹¹. In the IR spectra of metal chelates

no band is observed in the region 1362–3364 cm⁻¹ indicates the absence of enolic form of ligand in complexes. Coordinated site is supported by downward shift by 2 to 20 cm⁻¹ in νC=N azomethine¹² and 12–24 cm⁻¹ in νC=O enolic¹³. The new bands appeared in the region 611–620 and 512–520 which were absent in ligand may be due to formation of M–N and M–O bonds¹⁴.

The above arguments indicate that the ligands behave as bidentate and coordinate to metal ions through enolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra : The magnetic moments of Cu^{II} complexes are found to be well to 1.87 and 1.81 B.M. for L₁ and L₂ complexes respectively which is expected for octahedral structure. The electronic absorption spectra of Cu^{II} complexes show a broad band in the region 15699 cm⁻¹ and 27933 cm⁻¹ assignable to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} and is due to charge transfer spectra respectively, which is a characteristic of distorted octahedral stereo-chemistry¹⁵.

The magnetic moments of Co^{II} complexes are found

Table 2. Characteristic IR frequencies of the ligand and its metal complexes (cm⁻¹)

Compd.	O-H...N (H-bonded)	C=O -Lactone carbonyl	C=N Azomethine group	C=O Enolic	C=C Aromatic ring	C-N Aryl azomethine	M-O	M-N
C ₁₄ H ₁₂ ClNO ₃ (L ₁)	3364	1702	1650	1634	1575	1440	-	-
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cu]	-	1703	1631	1611	1573	1461	611	512
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Co]	-	1705	1648	1610	1562	1461	617	513
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Mn]	-	1720	1641	1610	1582	1463	618	513
[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Fe]Cl	-	1708	1648	1620	1576	1461	620	520
C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₄ (L ₂)	3362	1715	1660	1629	1580	1436	-	-
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Cu]	-	1714	1650	1621	1561	1460	618	541
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Co]	-	1713	1648	1610	1575	1460	612	540
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Mn]	-	1718	1640	1617	1578	1459	608	499
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Fe]Cl	-	1714	1646	1614	1574	1462	616	512

4.96 and 5.01 B.M. suggests octahedral geometry. The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes showed three absorption bands around 10163, 19305 and 23573 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively suggesting high spin octahedral geometry¹⁶.

The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes shows the absorption bands around 14948, 24691 and 31949 cm⁻¹ assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}(G)$ /charge transfer respectively. The magnetic moment values for Mn^{II} complexes are 5.85 and 5.98 B.M. These facts indicate that the complexes has octahedral geometry¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

The magnetic moment of Fe^{III} complexes 5.87 and 5.81 suggest the octahedral geometry. The Fe^{III} complex have expected four electronic absorption spectra due to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$. But all these four transition are not generally observed. In the present investigation three bands are observed around 15297-16181, 22936-24630 and 30769-32778 cm⁻¹, which may be, assigned to high spin octahedral complexes, for transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_1(D)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_1$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ respectively²⁰ corresponds to octahedral symmetry. The last d-d band assigned to transition ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ in the present case may be associated with the charge transfer band traveling into visible region of spectrum²¹.

Thermogravimetric analysis does not show a weight loss up to 300 °C, indicating absence of coordinated water and water of hydration. The Cu^{II} complex of ligand L₁ and L₂ are chosen for thermal study. Both complexes undergo decomposition in one stage which shows about 75% and 77% decomposition respectively. In order to calculate the kinetic parameters viz. *n* (order of reaction),

E (energy of activation), *Z* (pre exponential factor), ΔS (entropy change) and *G* (free energy change). Three methods have been used namely Coats-Redfern (C.R.)²², MacCallum-Tanner (M.T.)²³ and Horowitz-Metzger (H.M.)^{24,25}.

Coats-Redfern method :

$$\log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)T^2} \right] = \log \frac{ZR}{Eq} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{Ea}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{1}{T} \quad (1)$$

MacCallum-Tanner method :

$$\log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)} \right] = \log \frac{ZEa}{Rq} - 0.485E^{0.435} - \frac{0.449+0.217Ea}{T} \cdot 10^3 \quad (2)$$

Horowitz-Metzger method :

$$\log \left[\frac{1-(1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{(1-n)} \right] = \log \frac{ZRT_s^2}{Eaq} - \frac{Ea}{2.303RT_s} + \frac{Ea\theta}{2.303RT_s^2} \quad (3)$$

The frequency factor (*Z*) was calculated by,

$$\text{Intercept} = \log (ZR/qEa)$$

and the equation used for calculating entropy change (ΔS) is

$$\Delta S = 2.303 R \log Zh/kT_s.$$

Using the computer Microsoft Excel programmes the linear plots of the left-hand side of eqs. (1) and (2) versus $1/T$ and against $\theta = (T - T_s)$ for eq. (3) were drawn by the method of least squares for different values of 'n' (order of reaction) ranging from 0 to 3 with an increment of 0.01 and the corresponding correlation coefficient were evaluated. The highest value of correlation coefficient gave the correct value of 'n'. From the slope and intercept, E_a and Z values were calculated. Using E_a and Z values, the values of ΔS and ΔG were determined.

The values of n , E , Z , ΔS and ΔG estimated by all the three methods are in good mutual agreement (Table 3). The value of E is sufficiently high and is comparable with other observations²⁶.

The unit cell parameters for the given diffractogram are $a = 15.41923 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 7.72515 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 11.99757 \text{ \AA}$, with $\alpha = \gamma = 90.00^\circ$ and $\beta = 114.084^\circ$. The sample is found to be monoclinic in nature with space group $P2_1/m$. The experimental density value of the complex was determined by using specific gravity method²⁸, which is further used to calculate the volume of unit cell. The experimental and theoretical density values $1.736506 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and $1.751231 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ respectively of complexes found to be in good agreement within the limits of experimental error. The other parameters such as porosity and particle size were calculated and are 1.1428%, 246.3716 \AA respectively. The number of molecules (n) per unit cell were calculated using equation $\rho = nm/Nv$ and found 2 molecules per unit cell.

Table 3. Kinetic parameters derived from thermal analysis

[C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cu]		Cu(L ₁) ₂ Cl ₂			
	<i>n</i>	<i>E_a</i> (kJ/mol)	<i>Z/S</i>	<i>E_a</i> (kJ/mol)	<i>E_a</i> (kJ/mol)
C.R.	0.84	115.581	1.72E+10	-55.4667	119.931
M.T.	0.84	116.776	1.21E+12	-20.0935	118.3519
H.M.	1.05	192.1456	5.68E+21	165.08	179.1991
[C ₂₈ H ₂₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₈ Cu]		Cu(L ₂) ₂ Cl ₂			
	<i>n</i>	<i>E_a</i> (kJ/mol)	<i>Z/S</i>	<i>E_a</i> (kJ/mol)	<i>E_a</i> (kJ/mol)
C.R.	1.1	31.46448	1.32E+08	-98.2286	41.57737
M.T.	0.9	25.13099	109.0663	-214.722	47.23715
H.M.	0.95	40.68887	70.77697	-218.318	63.16525

The X-ray powder diffraction of Cu^{II} complex of L₁ is studied as a representative system. The observed 2θ with relative intensity more than 10% are indexed and have been used for evaluation. The 7 reflections of 2θ between 7.94 to 28.90 with maximum $2\theta = 12.08$ and $d = 7.31 \text{ \AA}$ are observed. The X-ray diffraction pattern of the complex with respect to their prominent peaks has been indexed by using computer software²⁷. The above index method also yielded miller indices (h, k, l) values (Table 4), unit cell parameters, volume of unit cell and space group.

Fungicidal activity :

The ligand and their corresponding metal chelates were screened by mycelial dry weight (MDW) method *in vitro* against *Aspergillus niger* for their fungicidal activity in glucose nitrate (GN) media. Medium prepared by adding 10 g of glucose, 2.5 g of KNO₃, 1 g of KH₂PO₄ and 0.5 g of MgSO₄ in 1 liter of distilled water and the fungus was cultivated on GN media. The ligand and complexes under investigation were added to GN medium (200 ppm and 400 ppm) preparing solutions/suspension. The conical

Table 4. XRD data of Cu^{II} complex

$2\theta_{\text{observed}}$	$2\theta_{\text{calculated}}$	<i>d</i> -observed (Å)	<i>d</i> -calculated (Å)	$\sin^2\theta_{\text{observed}}$	$\sin^2\theta_{\text{calculated}}$	<i>h,k,l</i>	Relative intensity
7.945	7.945	11.1190	11.119	0.004799	0.004799	-1,0,1	50.9
8.066	8.066	10.9532	10.952	0.004946	0.004946	0,0,1	70.5
12.085	12.085	7.3176	7.3175	0.011081	0.011081	1,0,1	100
14.010	14.017	6.3162	6.3129	0.014873	0.014889	0,1,1	8.7
26.065	26.065	3.4159	3.4158	0.050852	0.050852	1,2,1	19.3
26.300	26.298	3.3859	3.3861	0.051758	0.051748	2,2,0	9.5
28.905	28.894	3.0864	3.0875	0.062289	0.062244	-3,2,1	11.4

flask containing medium with ligand and complexes, autoclaved at 15 lbs for 30 min, inoculated with *A. niger*, after 168 h the mycelium obtained was collected by filtration through Whatman filter paper. The yield of MDW was recorded. The ligand exhibited toxicity in the inhibition. Due to synergistic combination of the coordinated metal ions with the ligands, the inhibition has been increased in complexes by 80 to 100%. The order of inhibition with respect to metal ion is $\text{Co} > \text{Fe} > \text{Mn} > \text{Cu}$. The results obtained are shown in Table 5. The results are similar to the observations made by other workers^{8,9}.

using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Molar conductivity was measured on a conductivity meter EQ-660 with a dip-type cell using $10^{-4} M$ solution of complexes in DMF.

The ligands are synthesized by mixing equimolar solution of dehydroacetic acid and 3-chloro aniline (L_1) and 3-amino phenol (L_2) in double distilled dry ethanol and reflux the mixture on 1RML rotamental for 6 h. The content was cooled to room temperature. The solid obtained was separated washed and recrystallised from ethanol. The purity of the ligand were checked by TLC, melting point, elemental analysis and characterized by IR and PMR.

Table 5. Yield of MDW in mg

Concentration (ppm)	Ligand	MDW (mg) in ligand	MDW (mg) control	MDW (mg) in complexes of			
				Mn ^{II}	Fe ^{III}	Co ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
200	L ₁	65	88	25	62	59	52
	L ₂	67	88	28	59	57	49
400	L ₁	30	88	25	28	17	20
	L ₂	32	88	18	27	15	6

Conclusions :

From the above discussion we proposed distorted octahedral geometry for the Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and octahedral geometry for Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes. The ligand behaves as ON bidentate coordinating through azomethine nitrogen and oxygen of enolic carbonyl group. The complexes are biologically active since they exhibit enhanced antifungal activities compared to their parent ligands. The thermal study of Cu^{II} complexes indicates that those are thermally stable. The XRD study suggests monoclinic P2/m crystal system.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents used in all preparative and analytical works were of A.R. grade. Dehydroacetic acid used for the preparation of ligand is of Merck. The micro analytical data for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen content in each sample were recorded on Elemental Analyzer Perkin-Elmer model no. 2400; IR spectra (nujol) in the range of $4000\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1b model no. C75430, ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand were measured in CDCl_3 . The AAS, TGA-DTA and XRD were recorded on Perkin-Elmer PE-Analyst 300, Ta/SDT-2960 and Philips 3701/Philips 1701 respectively. The UV-Vis spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes were done using a Gouy's balance at room temperature

Synthesis of metal complexes : To a hot solution of the ligand (2 mmol) in (30 ml) methanol, the metal chloride (1 mmol) in (20 ml) methanol was added dropwise with stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained by adding 10% methanolic solution of ammonia. The complexes of different metal ions were precipitated at different pH. It was then refluxed for 2–4 h. The resulting metal complex was filtered in hot condition and washed with chloroform, methanol, pet-ether ($40\text{--}60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and dried over calcium chloride in vacuum desiccators.

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